

Hydrochemical Assessment of the Hot Springs in Nyaungshwe and Taunggyi Townships, Shan State (South)

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Abstract

The detailed hydrochemical analysis was carried out on the bases of water samples collected from the hot springs in Nyaungshwe and Taunggyi townships, Shan state, (south). Hardness, pH, content of total dissolved solids, sulphate, iron, lead and arsenic are measured. As these measures are compared and correlated with WHO standard of drinking water. Lead and arsenic content of all samples from locations are suitable for drinking water. The result indicates that these water samples have acceptable for hardness, the total dissolved solids content and pH value of the WHO standard. Fe enrich in water samples of Sinte area.

Key words: Nyaungshwe, Taunggyi, Shan State, WHO, Sinte

Introduction

Today, the attention to environmental quality is greatly focused on water because of its importance in maintaining the human health and health of the ecosystem. Fresh water is finite resource, essential for agriculture, industry and even human existence. Without adequate quantity and quality of fresh water, sustainable development will not be possible.

The addition of various kinds of pollutants and nutrients through the agency sewage, industrial effluents, agricultural run-off etc. into the water bodies bring about a series of changes in the physio-chemical and characteristics of water, which have been the subject of several investigation.

Fresh water resource is at a faster rate of deterioration. The water quality is now a global problem. Discharge of toxic chemicals, over pumping of aquifer and contamination of water bodies with substance that promote algae growth are some of the today's major causes for water quality degradation.

Most of the hilly region faces problems to get fresh reliable water for drinking. As increasing the population, not only in quality but also in quantity, sustainable water to get is in high demand. Over the past decades, with the rapid industrialization and urbanization in Taunggyi and Ayetharyar, more water resource for industrial and domestic uses is required. The aim of present research is to access the quality in hydrochemical parameters of the water from the hot springs in Nyaungshwe and Taunggyi townships, southern Shan state, between latitude 20° 00' N and 21°00'N, longitude between 96°50' E and 97°10' E, covering one inch topographic map No . 93 H/1. Figure (1) shows location map of the research area.

Background Geology

Shan state (south) comprises of the rocks of older Paleozoic in age. Figure (2) shows regional geological map of the area. The exposed rock units of this area are Wunbye Formation and Linwe Formation.

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Wunbye Formation

It is named after the Wunbye Hill (1714 m) in Ywa-ngan township by MyintLwinThein (1973). The type section is located between the point at the eastern margin of Ingyi village (Ywa-ngantownship) and the locality about 24 km north of western margin of Nan-on village. The stratigraphic thickness at the type area is 1797 m.

It comprises limestone, dolomites with minor amount of siltstone. Bioturbation is common. Microbial lamination (stromatolite) is typical character of the limestone in the Wunbye Formation in this area. Limestones are fine-grained, whitish-grey to bluish-grey in colour, sometimes oolitic, dolomitic, and with pink, buff or yellow- coloured silty materials in the form of burrows, specks, patches and irregular or regular laminations. Dolomitic limestones are usually medium to thick bedded, sometimes with cross-laminations, generally highly jointed, soft to subindurated. Pb and Cu mineralization is associated with dolomitic limestone in this assigned area.

Parallel laminations, cross-laminations and bioturbated structures are locally present in the Wunbye Formation.

The lower boundary of the Wunbye Formation cannot be encountered, however the upper part is directly and conformably contact with the Nan-on Formation.

Brachiopods, nautiloid cephalopods, sponges, receptaculitid algae are present. On the basis of faunal assemblages, this formation can be defined as the Middle Ordovician in age. It can be therefore correlated with the Lower Naungkangyi Group of the northern Shan State.

Linwe Formation

The name of the Linwe Formation is given after the village of Linwe, 24 km NE of Ywa-ngan Township by MyintLwinThein (1973).

The type section of the Linwe Formation is located at Linwe village and its neighbourhood in Ywa-ngan township. The total thickness of this unit at the type section is 575 metre.

Linwe Formation consists of purple, pink and grey, medium to thick bedded, phacoidal limestones, fine-grained, poorly jointed, wavy discontinuous laminated, argillaceous limestone, bluish-grey calcareous shale and calcareous mudstones. Discontinuous wavy lamination and nodular bedding are common.

Linwe Formation is conformably underlain by Tanshauk purple shales. Locally the upper boundary is directly and conformably contact with overlying the Zebingyi Formation.

Michelinoceras are characteristic fauna in the phacoidal limestone and calcareous mudstones. Ostracods, crinoids, bryozoans, brachiopods are also common. The age of Linwe Formation is considered to be Early Silurian (MyintLwinThein, 1973). This unit is correlated with the Nyaungbaw Limestone (La Touche, 1913) of the northern Shan state.

Figure (1) Location Map of the research area

Figure (2) Regional geological map of the research area (MGS-2014)

Figure (3) Sample location map of the research area

The purple, pink or blue grey phacoidal textured limestone, argillaceous limestone, calcareous mudstone and shale sequence of the Pindaya and Bawsaing area is placed in the Late Ordovician due to the presence of conodonts (Wolfart *et. al.*, 1984). According to HlaThein (1991), age of the Linwe Formation is Early Silurian and can be correlated with the Nyaungbaw Formation in northern Shan State.

Geological Structure

The springs in this area occur as structurally controlled. Kyauk-Kyan fault (Win Swe and Win Naing, 2008) is striking N-S, which is left lateral strike slip fault through the investigated area. As these springs are related to this fault, occurring along the Kyauk-Kyan fault.

Method of Study

Water samples were collected from the hot springs in Taunggyi and Nyaungshwe area. Sample collected locations are as shown in figure (3). These samples are chemically tested in the laboratory of ISO.

Various physical and chemical parameters like P^H , total suspended solid, total dissolved solids, alkalinity, turbidity, hardness of calcium, magnesium are determined for different samples.

All probable safety measures were taken at every stage, starting from sample collection, storage, transportation, and final analysis of the samples to avoid contamination.

The results are analysed by comparing and correlating the WHO drinking water standard.

Result findings and Discussions

Hydrochemical analysis of water samples are tested under the categories of P^H , hardness, Total dissolved solids, chlorine, lead, arsenic and iron. The location of the springs are described in Table. (1). Hydrochemical analysis results are expressed in Table (2). Figure (4.a,b,c,d) shows springs in the research area.

Table.1 Location of the springs for sample collections.

Sample location	Easting	Northing
Khaungdaing	96° 53' 09.364" E	20° 36' 26.716" N
Yenway	96° 54' 24.317" E	20° 45' 23.594" N
Sinte	96° 56' 46.727" E	20° 54' 32.464" N
Pauktaw	96° 57' 13.496" E	20° 35' 59.947" N

Table.2 Hydrochemical assessment results

Parameter	Khaungdaing	Yenway	Sinte	Pauktaw	WHO
pH	6.9	6.7	6.8	6.9	7
Hardness (Ca)	112mg/l	172	208	242	500mg/l
Hardness (Mg)	5g	88	112	118	
Fe	0.26 mg/l	0.46*	0.52*	0.18	0.3mg/l
SO ₄	42 mg/l	48	42	158	200 mg/l
Suspended solid	15 mg/l	57	58	6	500 mg/l
Dissolved solid	302 mg/l	336	303	610	1000 mg/l
Pb	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	0.01 mg/l
As	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	0.01 mg/l

Figure (4a)

Figure (4b)

Figure (4a) - Hot water from the Khaungdaing spring.

Figure (4b) - Spring of Sinte village.

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Figure (4c) - Spring of Yenway Village

Figure (4d) - Spring of Pauktaw village.

The data for the hydrochemical analysis for samples from springs in research area are compared with WHO standard in graphic presentation (Figure 5).

Hardness

Although all water samples collected are acceptable standard of hardness by WHO, they are very hard according to the U.S.G.S classification.

Iron

Hot water from the Sinte containing 0.52 mg/l of iron which is highest content value in this area. Another location is Yenway in which iron content is 0.46 mg/l. These content values are higher than WHO standard of 0.3 mg/l. Hot water samples of Khaungdaing and Pauktaw area are acceptable standard for drinking water.

Iron is the one of the essential mineral for humans and animals. Degree of absorption depends upon solubility and stability of compound. It is a component of blood cells and liveral metalloenzymes. However, more than 10 mg per kg of body weight causes rapid respiration and pulse rates, congestion of blood vessels, hypertension and drowsiness. It increases hazard of pathogenic organisms, as many of them require Fe for their growth (U.S.E.P.A, 1976).

SO₄

Though SO₄ content is variation between 42 to 148 mg/l, these values are not beyond the WHO drinking water standard. All the samples collected are acceptable level of SO₄ by WHO.

Total Dissolved Solids

Total dissolved solids content in samples of hot water from the springs of Khaungdaing, Yenway and Sinte are relatively smaller value than those of occurred in Pauktaw.

But, according to the WHO standard, total dissolved solids in hot water from this research area are acceptable level by WHO, as well as U.S.G.S classification.

Lead and Arsenic

Fortunately, lead and arsenic are nil in the hot water samples collected in the research area.

Conclusion

Hydrochemical assessment results indicate that the p^H levels of all samples are acceptable.

Hardness, total dissolved solids, sulphate content, lead and arsenic content in all samples from all locations are suitable for drinking water.

Among the samples collected in research area iron concentration of water sample from Yenway and Sinte are posing risk for consumption.

Hardness, total dissolved solids, sulphate content, lead and arsenic content in all samples from locations are suitable for drinking water.

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